

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN BCS STEELS

Sample of steel	Vanadium content		% Deviation
	Found*	Certified value	
258/1	0.335 (0.340)	0.35	- 4.28
481	0.53 (0.54)	0.52	+1.92
410/1	0.24 (0.245)	0.23	+4.34

*Average of three determinations.

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Extraction-Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Copper(II) with Diphenylcarbazone

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DIPHENYLCARBAZONE forms chelate complexes with a number of metal ions¹. Copper(II) reacts with this reagent forming a red coloured complex which is extractable into isobutyl methyl ketone. Seno and Kakita² used this reagent for the determination of copper. In the present investigation, a spectrophotometric method for determination of copper in micro amounts using diphenylcarbazone as reagent is described. The method is simple, rapid, sensitive and selective.

Experimental

A Beckmann DK-2 spectrophotometer with quartz cuvettes of 1 cm thickness was used for absorbance measurements. The pH of the equilibrated aqueous phase was measured with a pH meter.

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. Stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving 1.96 g $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in double distilled water

containing a few drops of H_2SO_4 and was standardized by complexometric method³. The solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by dilution from the stock solution. A 0.02% solution of diphenylcarbazone (B.D.H.) in isobutyl methyl ketone was used as the reagent. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from the metal salts or from the sodium, potassium or ammonium salts of anions. Adjustment of pH of the aqueous phase was made with 0.2 M sodium acetate-0.2 M acetic acid.

Recommended procedure: An aliquot of the dilute copper solution containing 0.5 to 14 μg copper was made up to 5 ml, the pH adjusted to 5.6 and was shaken with 10 ml of 0.02% solution of diphenylcarbazone in isobutyl methyl ketone for 3 min. The organic layer was separated and the absorbance of the extract was measured at 540 nm against a reagent blank. The amounts of copper in unknown solutions were calculated from a calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The absorption spectrum of a solution of copper(II)-diphenylcarbazone complex in isobutyl methyl ketone (0.4 ppm copper) at pH 5.6 against a reagent blank is shown in Fig. 1A. The spectrum of the reagent blank vs the solvent is also shown in Fig. 1B. The maximum absorption of the complex is at 540 nm.

Effect of pH: The complex exhibited constant and maximum absorbance in the pH range 5.3 to 8.0. The effect of pH on the extraction of the complex is presented in Fig. 2. 0.5 to 14 μg copper

Fig. 1. A. Absorption spectrum of copper(II)-diphenylcarbazone complex in isobutyl methyl ketone (0.4 ppm Cu) against the reagent blank.

B. The spectrum of the reagent blank against the solvent.

NOTES

Fig. 2. Extraction of copper(II) as diphenylcarbazone complex.

can be extracted quantitatively by a single extraction with 10 ml of 0.02% reagent solution when the pH is maintained within this range.

Effect of reagent concentration: The effect of varying concentration of reagent on extraction of copper was studied. A 0.02% solution of the reagent was found to be most suited for quantitative extraction. At higher reagent concentration, the absorbance of the extract does not increase when measured against a reagent blank. At lower reagent concentration, extraction is incomplete.

Stability of the colour: The copper complex was found to be stable in the solvent for 8 hr. The absorbance of the complex is independent of temperature in the 25 to 35° range.

Conformity to Beer's law, sensitivity and precision: The copper(II)-diphenylcarbazone complex system conforms to Beer's law over the concentra-

tion range of 0.05 to 1.4 ppm copper. The molar absorptivity of the complex and Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction are $6.3 \times 10^4 \text{ l. mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.001 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$ copper, respectively.

A standard solution containing 5 μg copper was analysed 10 times by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.63 with a standard deviation of 0.005 absorbance unit and a relative error of $\pm 0.8\%$.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of foreign ions was studied by adding different amounts of foreign ions to 4 μg copper(II) and determining the copper, following the recommended procedure. It is found that Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Pt(IV), Ag(I), Au(III), Zn(II), Cd(II), Cr(III and VI), Mo(VI), W(VI), F^- , Br^- , I^- , oxalate, tartrate, sulphite and nitrite, when present in almost equal amounts and in five fold excess of copper, did not interfere. However, Pd(II), Hg(II) and Sn(II and IV), CN^- and EDTA interfered seriously and Fe(III) and SCN^- interfered only when present in five fold excess of copper. The interference due to Hg(II) could be removed by treating the extract with 0.1% solution of potassium iodide.

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